

Teachers' Pedagogical Skills, Job Commitment and Students' Learning Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State

Abdulkadir Tunde MOHAMMED

Department of Educational Management, University of Ilorin

muhammedabdulkadir559@gmail.com

Kamaldeen Olohundare SUYLYMAN

Department of Educational Foundations, Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State

sulymanko@fceiwo.edu.ng

Omosho Sulyman SHEHU

Department of Educational Management and Counselling, Al-Hikmah University, Kwara State

shehusuly@gmail.com

Rasheed Temitope JIMOH

Department of Educational Management, Kwara State University, Malete, Kwara State

rashtopsenior@gmail.com

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18140035>

Abstract

This study focused on teachers' pedagogical skills, job commitment and learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State. It used descriptive research design of correlational type. Four thousand, eight hundred and twenty-five SSS III students in the area formed the study population. All the 17 public secondary schools therein were selected purposively, while 356 SSS III students were selected proportionately. Data collection was done via the use of Pedagogical Skills Questionnaire (TPSQ), Job Commitment Questionnaire (JCQ) Students' Learning Effectiveness Questionnaire (SLEQ). The researchers ensured validity of the instruments. The reliability test conducted on the instruments yielded 0.83, 0.79, and 0.81 for TPSQ, JCQ and LEQ had respectively. Pearson product-moment correlation was used to test hypothesis one and two, while multiple regression was utilised for testing hypothesis three. The study found among others that there was a significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills, job commitment and students' learning effectiveness (f-value: 534.117, p-value: 0.011; beta

weights: .514, .044). It was concluded that teachers' pedagogical skills play an important role in enhancing learning effectiveness while job commitment is an important instrument which teachers need to be able to actualise learning effectiveness on the part of students. The study recommended that Osun State government should ensure that adequate and periodic capacity building programmes via workshop, symposium, conference, seminar, and lecture are organized for teachers, to continuously equip and update their pedagogical skills needed to process teaching in way that could enhance learning effectiveness.

Keywords: Commitment, Job, Learning Effectiveness, Pedagogical Skills, Teachers

Introduction

The position of teachers in education system is a very crucial and irreplaceable one. The reason is that they manipulate instructional resources made available in schools to give best instructional delivery and also guide students to ensure that effective learning takes place. However, every teacher needs many instruments to be able to effectively operate in the classroom and some of the instruments are pedagogical skills and job commitment. A teacher without adequate pedagogical skills and job commitment might not be able to drive instruction in such a way that students' learning effectiveness could be achieved.

Learning refers to the process by which students acquire new knowledge which facilitates change in their behavior. Akinyemi (2020) elucidated learning as the process by which a receiver (students) acquires knowledge from a sender (teacher). A learning process is said to be effective when students are able to understand and recall when asked. Learning effectiveness could also mean the extent to which the behavioural objectives of a particular lesson has been achieved in students. Mustafa et al. (2023) and Fowler (2018) believed that learning process is influenced and determined by environmental variables such as instructor engagement and social engagement. Salawu et al. (2022) saw learning as an inference drawn from an organism's performance which is a product of an enduring change of behaviour. Mustafa et al. (2023) stressed that in the process of learning, the behaviour of students is displayed and demonstrated via expectations of control of learning beliefs and self-efficacy.

Ikani et al. (2019) viewed pedagogy as the system of methods and principles which aid effective teaching and learning process. Shulman (2017) believed that pedagogy means the knowledge that an educator needs to have, and this consists of strategies and actions required for teaching and addressing the students' needs and planning of activities that stimulate students to learn effectively. Yusuf and Amali (2013) elucidated that pedagogical skills mean the knowledge about classroom management such as assessment and methods of student motivation; knowledge about students' personalities and their families; and socio-interactional skills. Based on this, every classroom teachers needs to have pedagogical skills, to be able to influence students' effective learning. Amosun and Kolawole (2015) emphasised that the significance pedagogical skills to teachers cannot be over-emphasised. It assists teachers to ponder on the best strategies, methods, resources, and materials to be used when imparting knowledge to students. Princewill et al. (2019) believed that the extent to which a teacher has pedagogical knowledge contributes in no minute quantity to the total actualisation of learning effectiveness. Haywood (2014) stated that for a teacher to be competent, he needs to possess good pedagogical skills and other skills such as self-reflection

skills, psychological skill, motivation skill, diagnostic skill and classroom management skill. Possession of all these skills assists teachers to actualise effective learning. Yusuf and Amali (2013) maintained that pedagogical skills possessed by teachers assist them to have a good and adequate knowledge of the subjects they teach and appreciate how the knowledge acquired overtime in their subject areas can be created, planned, and connected to other branches of knowledge. Princewill et al. (2019) stated a teacher with good pedagogical knowledge is likely to be competent, comprehend where learners may have problems with learning and have the ability to impart knowledge to students in a way that they could assimilate and achieve highly in the lessons. Ani (2018) believed that pedagogical skills revolve around the educators' understanding of preparation, design and implementation of instructional delivery, assessment of students' achievement in learning, and development of students to achieve various potentials in learning. Eno et al. (2025) opined that teachers with pedagogical skills are believed to be effective teachers and known for their dedication to the subject matter which they teach, and their commitment and passion to assisting students to actualise their best in the process of teaching and learning. Yusuf and Amali (2013) posited that pedagogical skills help teachers to be cognizant of the presumptions and contextual knowledge that students typically need to acquire in each subject; and of approaches and instructional materials that can be of help as well as assimilating and solving the difficulties that could arise in the classroom while imparting knowledge to students.

Job commitment refers to the extent to which teachers exhibit laudable passion towards the performance of their job. Irefin and Mechanic (2014) believed that workers with low job commitment is likely to have little urge for the effective attainment of the organisational goals. Job commitment is very important. It determines how effective teachers are, which in turn have effect on students' effective learning and academic performance. Negashe (2021) viewed job commitment as an attitude which shows the feelings such as identification, attachment, and loyalty to the school in which a teacher works. Ayele (2014) saw teachers' job commitment as the passionate connection between a teacher and the school as a formal organisation. If job commitment is high, it could lead to job motivation, thereby enhancing effective learning on the part of students. Odoh (2021) viewed job commitment of teachers as a great extent of the sense of attachment which a teacher displays towards a school. Altun (2017) opined that when a teacher is committed to the teaching profession, he is likely to be dedicated to students' academic progress and the end result could be improvement in learning and enhancement of students' academic performance. Emelugwo and Ukaigwe (2025) maintained that teachers who are committed are continuously interested in building their capacity. Committed teachers to the teaching profession always partner with other colleagues to encourage students to be serious to their learning. Usman (2018) found in his study that there was significant relationship between lecturer commitment and learning effectiveness among students in universities in Lagos State. The study conducted by Akinyemi (2020) revealed that teachers' job commitment had a significant effect on pupils' learning effectiveness in basic schools in Ifelodun Local Government, Kwara State.

Statement of the Problem

As gathered from some parents, members of the public, students in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government Area, Osun State, as well as the firsthand information got by the researchers via interaction with some stakeholders, pedagogical skills and job commitment of some teachers in public secondary schools in the area seem inadequate and ineffective. Some teachers do not have what it takes to strategically manage classrooms, determine strategies or methodologies needed to impart knowledge to students, detect and handle issues which could cause distraction for each student or entire students while imparting knowledge to them. Not only that, the passion which some teachers have for the teaching profession is not strong enough. This might be the cause of lateness to work, intentional skipping of lessons, absconding, absenteeism, ineffective teaching and utilisation of instructional materials, poor preparation of lesson plan and ineffective assessment of students to properly determine their progress in learning. All these might be part of the factors causing ineffective learning among students.

Some studies which are relevant to this study have been carried out by scholars in the field of education. For instance, Akinyemi (2020) investigated the effect of teachers' job commitment had on pupils' learning effectiveness in basic schools in Ifelodun Local Government, Kwara State. Usman (2018) conducted a study on lecturers' job commitment and learning effectiveness among students in universities in Lagos State. Alani (2019) examined the relationship between teachers' job commitment and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Aderibigbe (2020) worked on the influence of teachers' job commitment on learning effectiveness among basic school pupils in Kaima Local Government, Kwara State. Oladapo (2023) researched on teachers' job commitment and learning effectiveness in basic schools in Idanre Local Government, Ondo State. However, no previous studies among the ones mentioned above focused on teachers' pedagogical skills, job commitment and students' learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State. Therefore, this was the observed academic lacuna which this study aimed to fill.

Purpose of the Study

The study:

- i. investigated the relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills and students' learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State;
- ii. examined the relationship between teachers' job commitment and students' learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State; and
- iii. investigated the relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills, job commitment and students' learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State; and

Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills and students' learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State.

H02: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ job commitment and students’ learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State.

H03: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ pedagogical skills, job commitment and students’ learning effectiveness in public secondary schools in Iwo Local Government, Osun State.

Methodology

Descriptive research design of correlational type was employed by the researchers to conduct the study. All 4,825 senior secondary school (SSS) III students in Iwo Local Government Area in 2024/2025 academic session constituted population of the study. The reason only the final year students formed the population was that the researchers believed that they had successfully completed two academic sessions and for that, they had more knowledge about their teachers than SSS I and II students. All the 17 public secondary schools in the area were purposively selected for the study because they were owned and financed by Osun State government. Via the use of proportionate sampling technique, a sample of 356 SSS III students was derived from 4,825 in the schools in the area, using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for deriving sample from population. Teachers’ Pedagogical Skills Questionnaire (TPSQ), Job Commitment Questionnaire (JCQ) Students’ Learning Effectiveness Questionnaire (SLEQ) were utilised for gathering data for the study. Each of the instruments had 10 items and response of option of Strongly Disagree scored 1, Disagree adjudged 2, Agree rated 3 and Strongly Agree considered 4 was used for scoring. Validity of the instruments was ensured by three experts in the field of education, while their reliability test conducted showed that TPSQ, JCQ and LEQ had 0.83, 0.79 and 0.81 respectively. Hypothesis testing was done via the use of Pearson product-moment correlation for the number one and two, while multiple regression was used for the number three. Out of the 356 copies of the instrument, only the 331 copies returned to the researchers were given to the statistician for analysis.

Results

Table 1

Teachers’ Pedagogical Skill and Learning Effectiveness

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Cal. r-value	p-value	Decision
Teachers’ Pedagogical Skills	331	2.41	.72	.606	.001	Ho ₁ Rejection
Learning Effectiveness	331	2.64	.82			

Source: Field Study, 2025

As presented on Table 1, the calculated r-value is .606, while the p-value which is .001 is less than 0.05 which is the level of significance. Hence, rejection was considered for the hypothesis one (Ho₁). This signifies that there was a significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills and students' learning effectiveness.

Table 2

Job Commitment and Learning Effectiveness

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Cal. r-value	p-value	Decision
Teachers' Pedagogical Skills	331	2.36	.55			
				.623	.005	Ho ₂ Rejection
Learning Effectiveness	331	2.64	.82			

Source: Field Study, 2025

As shown on Table 2, .623 is the calculated r-value, while .001 which is the p-value is less than the level of significance, 0.05. Therefore, hypothesis two (Ho₁) was rejected. This means that there was a significant relationship between job commitment and students' learning effectiveness.

Table 3a

Model Summary of Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.615 ^a	.372	.371	.681234

Source: Field Study, 2025

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Mentoring, Recruitment Process

As reflected is Table 3a, the calculated r-value (R) is .515^a while the multiple correlation (R²) is 3.72. Based on the outcome, the R² value (.372), as shown on the Table, depicts that the teachers' pedagogical skills and job commitment had a joint contribution of 37% on students' learning effectiveness. Therefore, other variables not looked into in this study accounted for the remaining 63%.

Table 3b

Result of Regression Analysis

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig	Decision
Regression	170.708	2	370.002			
Residual	214.600	120	.272	534.117	0.011	Rejected
Total	384.338	122				

Source: Field Study, 2025

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Effectiveness

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers' Pedagogical Skills, Job Commitment

As presented by Table 3b, 534.117 is the calculated F-value while the p-value is 0.011. Hence, because 0.011 which is the p-value is less than 0.05 that represents the significance level, hypothesis three (Ho3) was rejected. This shows that there was a significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills, job commitment and students' learning effectiveness.

Table 3c

Contributions of Teachers' Pedagogical Skills and Job Commitment to Students' Learning Effectiveness

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.430	.083		17.483	.000
TEACHERS' PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS	.694	.035	.514	15.337	.000
JOB COMMITMENT	.086	.042	.044	1.945	.028

Source: Field Study, 2025

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Effectiveness

Table 3c presented the relative contribution of teachers' pedagogical skills and job commitment (independent variables) to students' learning effectiveness (independent variable). As presented in the table, p-value and calculated t-value of teachers' pedagogical skills were 0.000 and 15.337 respectively, while that of job commitment were 1.945 and .028 respectively at 0.05 level of significance. This means that teachers; pedagogical skills and job commitment had significant joint

contribution to students' learning effectiveness. Furthermore, through the Beta weight, the table presented that the contribution of teachers' pedagogical skills which was .514 is greater than that of job commitment which was .044. Therefore, considering this finding, it can be concluded that every unit increase in the students' learning effectiveness would be determined by .514 unit of teachers' pedagogical skills and .044 unit of job commitment. Therefore, teachers' pedagogical skills and job mentoring had significant contribution to students' learning effectiveness.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that there was a significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills and students' learning effectiveness. This finding is in tandem with the finding of Oladapo (2023) that there was a significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills and learning effectiveness in basic schools in Idanre Local Government, Ondo State. The finding also agrees with the finding of Aderibigbe (2020) that teachers' pedagogical skills has a significant influence on learning effectiveness among basic school pupils in Kaima Local Government, Kwara State.

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between job commitment and students' learning effectiveness. This finding corroborates the finding of Usman (2018) that lecturers' job commitment had a significant effect on learning effectiveness among students in universities in Lagos State. The finding confirms the finding of Alani (2019) which revealed that there was a significant relationship between teachers' job commitment and students' learning effectiveness in secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

The findings of the study found that there was a significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical skills, job commitment and students' learning effectiveness. This finding supports the position of Aderibigbe (2020) that pedagogical skills is one of the instrument which every teacher needs to possess. A teacher without effective pedagogical skills lacks a great instrument to professionally operate in the classroom a way that could enhance effective teaching and consequently facilitate effective learning. The finding corroborates the assertion of Oladapo (2023) that poor possession of pedagogical skills is one of the factors hampering effective teaching of some students in secondary school in Nigeria and poor students' academic performance. If pedagogical skills of a teacher are okay, he stands the chance to handle lesson presentation properly and consequently achieve high level of level effectiveness. The finding agrees with the position of Usman (2018) that job commitment of every teacher is very essential in school system. The moment job commitment starts having problem, job performance and learning effectiveness on the part of students are likely to suffer. The finding is also in tandem with the position of Alani (2019) that no matter how a school is adequately provided with physical facilities and equipped with instructional resources and furniture, if the job commitment of teachers is not strong, effective learning effectiveness might not be achieved by students.

Conclusion

The study concluded that teachers' pedagogical skills play an important role in enhancing learning effectiveness while job commitment is an important instrument which teachers need to be able to actualise learning effectiveness on the part of students.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- i. Osun State government should ensure that adequate and periodic capacity building programmes on pedagogy via workshop, symposium, conference, seminar, and lecture are organized for teachers, to continuously equip and update their pedagogical skills needed to process teaching in way that could enhance learning effectiveness; and
- ii. teachers should intensify their effort in showing more dedication, passion, and loyalty to the teaching profession, to boost their morale towards improvement in job performance and consequently enhance learning effectiveness.

References

- Aderibigbe, R. E. (2020). Influence of teachers' job commitment on learning effectiveness among basic school pupils in Kaima Local Government, Kwara State. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 2(2), 57-63.
- Akinyemi, J. L. (2020). Effects of teachers' job commitment on pupils' learning effectiveness in basic schools in Ifelodun Local Government, Kwara State. *Journal of Science and Technological Education*, 7(2), 62-71.
- Altun, M. (2017). The effects of teacher commitment on student achievement. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 3(3), 51-54.
- Ayele, D. (2014). *Teachers' job satisfaction and commitment in general secondary schools of Hadiya Zone in southern nation nationality and people of the regional state*. A Ph.D. Thesis, Institute of Development Studies and Partner Organisations, Malaysia.
- Amosun, M. D., & Kolawole, O. A. (2015). Pedagogical knowledge and skill competences of pre-school teachers in Ibadan metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of International Science and Technical Education*, 19(2), 6-14.
- Ani, U. L. (2018). Impact of teachers' pedagogical skills and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(2), 67-73.
- Emelugwo, I. C., & Ukaigwe, P. C. (2025). Teachers' commitment and job performance in public senior secondary schools In Anambra State. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research* 13(2), 128-138.
- Eno, V. I., Zainab, Z. O., Utsu, E. A., & Akpanudi, G. A. (2025). Influence of teachers' pedagogical competencies on junior secondary school students' performance in Social Studies in Kontagora, Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of English Language Teaching*, 13(1), 1-11.
- Fowler, S. (2018). *The motivation to learn online questionnaire*. A Ph.D. Thesis, University of Georgia. Retrieved from https://getd.libs.uga.edu/pdfs/fowler_kevin_s_201805_phd.pdf

- Haywood, G. (2014). *Improving quality in education: Dynamic approaches to school improvement*. Taylor and Francis Group.
- Ikani V. I., Eyong, E. I., & Ejue H. F. (2019). Pedagogical competencies of teachers and performance of junior secondary students in Social Studies in Kontagora Local Government Area, Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 3(13), 322-332.
- Irefin, P. & Mechanic, M. A. (2014). Effect of employee commitment on organizational performance in Coca Cola Nigeria Limited, Maiduguri, Borno State. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19(3), 33-41.
- Mustafa, N. C., Amali, N. A. K., Rahmat, N. H, Seng, H. Z., & Ibrahim, I. W. (2023). Exploring online learning motivation among undergraduates through social cognitive theory. *International Journal of Academic Research I Business and Social studies*, 13(3), 1447-1464.
- Negashe, A. (2021). *Teacher's job satisfaction and relationship with organizational commitment at government secondary schools of Gulele Sub City*. A Ph.D. Thesis, St. Mary's University, Ethiopia
- Odoh, J. N. (2021). Relationship between school climates and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 7, 479-502.
- Oladapo, K. I. (2023). Teachers' job commitment and learning effectiveness in basic schools in Idanre Local Government, Ondo State. *African Journal of Education*, 2(1), 54-62.
- Princewill, I., Egwuasi, N. F., Nnodi, I., & Aniefiok S. U. (2019). Teachers' pedagogical skills and students' learning of English language in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *DEV SANSKRITI: Interdisciplinary International Journal*, 13, 47-68.
- Shulman, R. Y. (2017). The Hidden side of the work: Teacher Knowledge Learning to teach. *Language Hatching* 35, 1-3.
- Usman, T. O. (2018). Lecturers' job commitment and learning effectiveness among students in universities in Lagos State. *Journal of Educational Counselling*, 2(2), 45-53.
- Yusuf, M. O., & Amali, B. A. (2013). Assessment of the level of pedagogical skills among professional teachers in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(3), 1-16.